

Relationships between Instrumental Texture, Sensory Evaluation, Biochemical Properties and Consumer Perception of Fufu Quality Attributes

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ABSTRACT

Fufu, a staple food in West Africa, is highly valued for its distinct texture, flavor, and color, the key traits that drive consumer acceptance. This study aims at determining the relationship between evaluation of fufu sensory traits by trained sensory panellists using — Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA) method, instrumental texture analysis, color measurements, and consumer preferences. Fufu was produced from cassava roots sourced from the National Root Crops Research Institute (NRCRI), Umudike, Nigeria. The study followed the RTBfoods harmonized Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for fufu production, sensory characterization, and instrumental measurements. Texture analysis was performed using a Stable Microsystems TA.XT plus texture analyzer, and color measurements were conducted with a Minolta CR-400 Chromameter, with parameters reported in the CIELAB color system. Consumer acceptability testing involved 124 participants in Umuahia South LGA, Abia State, Nigeria, who evaluated fufu samples using a 9-point hedonic scale for attributes such as texture, color, and overall acceptability. Trained panelists also evaluated key sensory attributes, including hardness, smoothness, mouldability, stickiness and stretchability, using QDA. Statistical analysis revealed significant correlations between consumer preferences and instrumental measurements. Specifically, consumer preference for mouldability negatively correlated with instrumental hardness, gumminess, adhesiveness, and all components of color (a^* , b^* , L^*), while correlating positively with cohesiveness and springiness. Also, consumer preference for smoothness negatively correlated with adhesiveness and gumminess. Results also showed a strong alignment between QDA and consumer testing, with key textural attributes such as moldability and smoothness being highly valued by consumers. Biochemical properties also showed significant impact on sensory traits. The findings indicate that attributes like swelling power, solubility, free sugar, Dry matter content (DMC), amylose and amylopectin play significant roles in determining the texture and color of fufu. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) further revealed that consumer preferences and sensory attributes varied across cassava genotypes. Genotypes Nwaocha, Baba70, TMEB419, and TMS980505 exhibited favorable sensory properties such as smoothness, moldability, stretchability and cohesiveness, aligning with consumer preferences. These findings highlight the importance of integrating food quality traits such as textural and color of food products into breeding selection index in order to meet the needs of end users especially fufu consumers. The integration of consumer testing, QDA, and instrumental analysis provides a comprehensive understanding of fufu quality, offering insights for cassava breeders and food processors in optimizing fufu production.

Key Words: Fufu, QDA, Instrumental texture, Color measurements, Consumer test

1 OVERVIEW

Fufu, a staple food in West Africa made primarily from cassava, is valued for its distinct texture, aroma, and color—attributes that are central to consumer satisfaction. Previous studies (Teeken *et al.*, 2022; Olaosebikan *et al.*, 2022; Teeken *et al.*, 2021; Ndjouenkeu *et al.*, 2021; Bello *et al.*, 2020) have shown that both processors and consumers prioritize texture and color when evaluating fufu. Assessing fufu's quality involves a range of methodologies, each offering insights into its sensory and physical characteristics. Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA), conducted by trained panels, provides a detailed sensory profile, capturing subtle variations in texture, aroma, color and appearance. Alongside this, instrumental methods such as texture analysis and chromameter-based color measurement objectively assess physical attributes, including hardness, stretchability, cohesiveness, adhesiveness and color parameters (L^* , a^* , b^* values). Consumer testing complements these methods by gauging overall acceptability and preferences from the consumer's perspective. This study explores the relationship between QDA, instrumental texture and color measurements, and consumer sensory attributes in the evaluation of fufu quality.

1.1 Procedure: Sample Preparation

Fresh cassava roots were sourced from the genetic gain experimental field at the National Root Crops Research Institute (NRCRI), Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria. Fufu processing followed the method outlined by Chijioke *et al.* (2021), where the cassava wet paste was processed into a dough-like product using the procedure described by Obilie *et al.* (2003). This cooking method involved continuous stirring of the reconstituted fufu paste under steady heat for approximately 5 minutes, as specified in the RTBfoods harmonized standard operating procedure (SOP).

1.1.1 Texture Analyzer

The Textural Profile Analysis (TPA) of fufu was conducted using a Stable Microsystems TA.XT plus texture analyzer, fitted with a standard cylindrical compression plate of 100 mm diameter. Prior to testing, the texture analyzer was powered on, and the PC was properly connected for data acquisition. TPA test parameters were selected from the instrument's library, and a project folder was created to store the analysis results. Calibration of the probe height and applied force was performed according to the manufacturer's guidelines. Fufu samples with uniform dimensions of 4.0 cm in height and 4.7 cm in diameter were positioned centrally on the instrument's platform, and the sample temperature was equilibrated to 45°C. The analysis was initiated via the instrument software, and double compression tests were executed automatically, applying a 10g trigger force with a 10-second interval between compressions.

Figure 1 : Texture Analyzer

1.1.2 Chromameter Reading

The color of cassava fufu dough was measured using a Chromameter Minolta CR-400 (Konica Minolta, Japan), with results reported according to the CIELAB color system. The instrument was calibrated using a standard white reference ($L^* = 93.30$, $a^* = 0.32$, $b^* = 0.33$). To ensure consistency, the surface of each fufu sample was manually levelled prior to measurement. The measuring head was positioned at two different points on each sample, and measurements were performed in triplicate. The color parameters were expressed as L^* (lightness, ranging from 0 [black] to 100 [white]), a^* (positive values indicate redness, negative values indicate greenness), and b^* (positive values indicate yellowness, negative values indicate blueness).

Figure 2 : Chromameter for color detection

1.1.3 QDA (Sensory Evaluation)

A sensory evaluation was conducted with 12 trained panellists. Each panellist received a 20 g portion of fufu, served at 45°C on white plastic disposable plates. To assess the homogeneity and repeatability of panel performance, each fufu variety was presented twice: five samples were evaluated during a morning session, with duplicate samples assessed in the afternoon session. Panellists evaluated the samples based on key sensory attributes, including color and texture.

Figure 3 : Sensory evaluation

1.1.4 Consumer Testing

A consumer acceptability study was conducted using 124 panelists on fufu samples using the RTBfoods (Roots, Tubers, and Bananas) harmonized Standard Operating Procedures (SOP). This standardized approach ensures consistent evaluation of sensory attributes across different studies, facilitating reliable comparisons. The study took place in Umuahia South LGA, Abia State, Nigeria, a region known for its significant consumption of fufu, making it an ideal location to assess local consumer preferences.

The participants were selected based on a balanced demographic profile, with an equal representation of both genders: 57 males and 67 females. The age range of the participants spanned from 18 to 65 years, with the majority falling within the 25–45 age group, ensuring a diverse mix of young adults and middle-aged individuals. Each participant was provided with a structured questionnaire to rate degree of likeness of fufu sensory attributes such as texture, color, and overall acceptability, using a 9-point hedonic scale, where 1 represented "dislike extremely" and 9 represented "like extremely."

The study aimed to capture consumer perceptions and preferences for fufu sensory properties, with the large sample size (124 individuals) ensuring robust data for statistical analysis. These results were later analyzed to identify correlations between consumer preferences, trained panel evaluations, and instrumental measurements for fufu texture and color, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of fufu quality attributes from both subjective and objective perspectives.

1.1.5 Biochemical Analysis of Cassava Attributes

Water Absorption Capacity (WAC): WAC was determined using the method described by Sathe and Salunkhe (1981). Approximately 1 g of sample was mixed with 10 mL of distilled water in a centrifuge tube, stirred for 30 minutes, and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes. The supernatant was decanted, and the weight of the sediment was recorded. WAC was calculated as the weight of water absorbed per gram of sample (g/g).

Bulk Density: Bulk density was measured using the method of Wang and Kinsella (1976). A 10 g sample was gently poured into a 50 mL graduated cylinder and tapped 10 times to remove void spaces. The final volume was recorded, and bulk density was calculated as the weight of the sample divided by its volume (g/mL).

Solubility and Swelling Power: The solubility and swelling power were determined following Leach et al. (1959). A 1 g sample was suspended in 10 mL of distilled water and heated at 90°C for 30 minutes. After cooling, the mixture was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes. The supernatant was evaporated to dryness to determine solubility, and the weight of the sediment was used to calculate swelling power as a ratio of sediment weight to initial dry sample weight.

Dispersibility: Dispersibility was assessed by dispersing 10 g of the sample in 100 mL of distilled water and stirring vigorously for 10 minutes. The mixture was allowed to settle for 3 hours, and the volume of dispersed solids was measured as a percentage of the total volume.

Starch Content: The starch content was determined using the anthrone method. A 0.1 g sample was hydrolyzed in 5 mL of 6 M HCl for 2 hours at 100°C. After neutralization with NaOH, the solution was reacted with anthrone reagent and incubated at 100°C for 10 minutes. The absorbance was read at 620 nm, using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1800) and starch content was calculated using a standard glucose calibration curve.

Free Sugar Content: Free sugar was quantified using the phenol-sulfuric acid method. A 0.1 g sample was dissolved in 5 mL of distilled water, and 1 mL of the extract was reacted with 1 mL of phenol solution (5%) and 5 mL of concentrated sulfuric acid. After cooling, absorbance was measured at 490 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1800), and sugar content was derived from a glucose standard curve.

Amylose and Amylopectin: Amylose and amylopectin contents were determined by iodometric method. A 0.1 g sample was dissolved in 1 mL of 95% ethanol and 9 mL of 1 N NaOH and incubated in a water-bath for 10 minutes at 80°C and then allowed to cool. 1ml of the mixture was pipette into a cleaned test tube and diluted with 9mls of distilled water. 0.5ml of the diluted mixture was then pipetted into another test tube and 0.1 ml of acetic acid solution and 0.2ml of potassium iodide reagent was added. The solution was made up using 9.2mls of distilled water and the absorbance was measured at 620 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1800). Amylose content was calculated using a standard formula, and amylopectin content was derived as the difference between 100 and amylose content value.

Crude Fiber Content: Crude fiber was measured using the AOAC 973.18 method. Samples were digested with 1.25% sulfuric acid and 1.25% sodium hydroxide solutions, followed by filtration and washing with hot water. The residue was dried at 105°C, weighed, and incinerated at 550°C. Crude fiber was calculated as the difference in weight before and after ashing.

Dry Matter Content: Dry matter content was determined using oven drying method. 10 g of the sample was weighed and dried in a hot air oven at 105°C until a constant weight was achieved. The dry weight was recorded, and dry matter was calculated as a percentage of the initial sample weight.

1.2 Statistical Analysis

Correlation analysis was conducted to evaluate the relationships among consumer traits, instrumental traits, sensory traits, and biochemical traits. This analysis provided insights into how these trait categories influence each other and their potential combined impact on cassava quality.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed to further explore the multivariate structure of the data, identifying key traits contributing to variation among samples and visualizing the relationships among traits. The PCA results were presented as a biplot to highlight the associations between consumer preferences, instrumental measurements, sensory evaluations, and biochemical properties, enabling a holistic interpretation of trait interactions.

All statistical analyses were conducted using R software (version 4.4.1), utilizing the *ggplot2*, *FactoMineR*, and *corrplot* packages for visualization and interpretation.

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

2.1 Correlations between Hedonic consumer scores and Instrumental texture

Figure 4 illustrates the relationship between result of consumer testing (using hedonic scale) and instrumental texture measurements. There was a notable correlation between consumers' preferences and objective texture measurements. Specifically, mouldability as rated by consumer was negatively correlated with instrumental hardness ($r = -0.66$), gumminess ($r = -0.74$), adhesiveness ($r = -0.73$) and all components of color ($a^* : r = -0.93$, $b^* : r = -0.99$, $L^* : r = -0.67$) while showing positive correlations with instrumental cohesiveness ($r = 0.53$) and springiness ($r = 0.54$). This indicates that consumers associate higher mouldability with softer, less gummy, less adhesive and more cohesive and moderately springy fufu. Smoothness from consumer also exhibited negative correlations with adhesiveness ($r = -0.39$) and Gumminess ($r = -0.37$). These relationships highlight consumers' preference for fufu with smooth texture, indicating that a smooth fufu, tends to be less adhesive and gummy.

Again, consumer color correlated negatively with components of instrumental color ($b^* = -0.89$, $a^* = -0.89$, $L^* = -0.47$). Chromameter expresses color in CIE (1976) color space with L^* for lightness, a^* for red-green and b^* for yellow-blue. The strong negative correlation observed implies that consumers dislike fufu within the red-green and yellow-blue color space. Furthermore, an intense bright colored fufu might also be disliked moderately by consumers.

Softness, however, showed weak correlations with all the instrumental parameters, implying that consumer perception of softness may not align as strongly with instrumental texture readings.

Correlation coefficient (r) of 25 – 40% is significant at $P < 0.05$, r of 41 – 60% is significant at $P < 0.01$, while r of 61 – 100% is significant at $P < 0.001$

Figure 4 : Correlation between the Hedonic consumer scores and Instrumental texture measurements

2.2 Correlations between Hedonic consumer scores and QDA

The result revealed a significant relationship between consumer testing using the hedonic scale and sensory evaluation through Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA). As shown in the Figure 5, a positive and significant correlation was observed between consumer and sensory mouldability ($r = 0.96$), as well as consumer and sensory smoothness ($r = 0.70$). However, a negative correlation was noted for color ($r = -0.48$).

Positive correlations observed in consumer and QDA mouldability and smoothness suggest that consumers' perception of these attributes aligns well with trained sensory panel evaluations, indicating consistency in these qualities.

The strong correlations between consumer hedonic and QDA indicate that QDA scores can also be employed for assessing consumers' preferences, and both approaches provide complementary insights into fufu quality.

Correlation coefficient (r) of 25 – 40% is significant at $P < 0.05$, r of 41 – 60% is significant at $P < 0.01$, while r of 61 – 100% is significant at $P < 0.001$

Figure 5 : Correlation between the Hedonic consumer scores and sensory evaluation (QDA)

2.3 Impact of Biochemical Attributes on Sensory Qualities

Figure 6 shows the relationships between different biochemical attributes and sensory qualities (smoothness, softness, mouldability and color) of fufu. Mouldability improves with higher swelling power (sp), solubility, free sugar, amylopectin and dispersibility, but decreases with water absorption capacity (WAC), dry matter content (DMC), amylose and crude fiber. Smoothness is positively influenced by swelling power, solubility, starch, amylopectin and free sugar, but is reduced by higher levels of DMC, WAC and amylose. Softness increases with bulk density while swelling power reduces it. Color improves with increased free sugar, swelling power, solubility and amylopectin, but is negatively affected by DMC, crude fibre, amylose and WAC.

Overall, the findings indicate that attributes like swelling power, solubility, free sugar, DMC, amylose and amylopectin play significant roles in determining the texture and color of the product, with notable trade-offs between these properties affecting different sensory qualities.

DMC: Dry Matter Content, SP: Swelling Power, WAC: Water Absorption Capacity. Correlation coefficient (r) of 25 – 40% is significant at $P < 0.05$, r of 41 – 60% is significant at $P < 0.01$, while r of 61 – 100% is significant at $P < 0.001$

Figure 6 : Correlation of Biochemical Attributes with Sensory traits (QDA)

2.4 PCA of Instrumental, Sensory, and Consumer Testing Attributes for Fufu Texture Preference

The PCA biplot (Figure 7) shows the distribution of cassava clones and traits along the first two principal components, PC1 and PC2, which explain 44.61% and 25.93% of the variance, respectively.

Sensory Traits (S_{traits}) such as s mouldability showed strong positive correlation with consumers mouldability (c -mould). This implies that consumers' perception of mouldability aligns with sensory evaluation by trained panelists. A close association was also observed between sensory stretchability and stickiness. Again, sensory smoothness exhibited weak correlation with consumer smoothness, this also implies an alignment of panelists evaluation and consumers perception of smoothness. Consumer softness on the other hand, seems not to align with sensory or instrumental parameters, indicating there might be inconsistency in understanding and evaluation of this trait.

Color traits such as L^* color (lightness) correlated positively with sensory color, indicating consistency in these measurements, however, consumer color showed a negative correlation with a^* and b^* color space. This negative correlation is suggestive of consumers' less preference for fufu dough within red-green and yellow-blue color space.

Impact of biochemical traits on quality attributes of fufu, showed that mouldability and smoothness are strongly influenced by free sugar, swelling power, solubility, amylopectin and starch content. Dry matter content (DMC) and amylose are negatively correlated with smoothness and mouldability, suggesting that higher DMC impacts negatively on fufu smoothness and mouldability.

Furthermore, the result showed that Nwaocha and TMS980505 are closely related to texture smoothness and mouldability, indicating that Nwaocha and 980505 may show high level of smoothness and mouldability. Contrarily, Baba 70 could exhibit high stickiness and stretchability while TMEB419 is closely associated with Instrumental cohesiveness.

S_: sensory, C_: Consumer, DMC: Dry Matter Content, SP: Swelling Power, WAC: Water Absorption Capacity, dispers: dispersibility, a_col: a* color (yellowishness), b_col: b* color (bluishness), L_col: L* color (lightness), CF: crude fibre, C_soft: consumer softness, I_hard: Instrumental hardness, stick: stickiness, stretch: stretchability, resil: resilience, chew: cheiness, solub: solubility, B_density: Bulk density, smooth: smoothness, amylop: amylopectin, mould: mouldability

Figure 7 : PCA of instrumental and sensory texture, consumer test score and biochemical properties of fufu from cassava clones

2.5 Trait Clusters and Quality Implications

Three primary clusters of traits emerge, each shaping cassava quality in unique ways:

The Texture-Smoothness Cluster which includes C_texture preference, C_smoothness preference, S_smooth, and I_hard, indicating that consumers favor doughs that are firm and smooth, supported by instrumental measurements of hardness.

The Moldability-Handling Cluster which includes C_moldability preference, S_mould, S_stretch, and I_cohes, showing that consumers prefer cohesive, moldable doughs that are easier to shape and handle, aligning with sensory and instrumental cohesiveness.

The Biochemical-Texture Cluster which includes Starch, Amylose, DMC, WAC, I_cohes, and I_spring make up this cluster, revealing that high starch and amylose contents lead to firmer, cohesive textures, which in turn support specific consumer preferences like texture and moldability.

The detailed relationships among instrumental, consumer, sensory, color, and biochemical traits reveal how cassava quality for fufu production is a function of integrated characteristics. Consumer preferences for specific texture and color traits can be traced back to instrumental and biochemical properties, informing breeders on which traits to focus on to develop cassava clones that meet processing and consumer standards. This understanding enables targeted selection of cassava varieties with optimal sensory and instrumental quality for fufu production.

2.6 Implication of the Study

The findings from this study reveal a strong alignment between consumer perceptions of fufu dough texture (using hedonic scale) and instrumental measurements of its physical properties. The significant correlations between hedonic attributes and their corresponding instrumental measures, provide critical insights into how sensory qualities perceived by consumers can be quantitatively assessed using objective methods.

Moreover, the study highlights that consumers' perception of stickiness, smoothness, and stretchability align closely with the instrumental texture measures, suggesting that these characteristics are critical to fufu quality. Notably, consumers prefer a softer fufu with more cohesion, and these findings can help in the development of fufu varieties that meet both sensory and texture preferences. This is particularly important for fufu producers aiming to enhance product appeal and satisfaction.

Furthermore, the trade-off between color and textural attributes—such as the negative correlation of color with stickiness and stretchability—implies that while texture is paramount in determining consumer preference, deviations in color can detract from overall acceptability. This suggests that fufu quality improvement efforts need to balance both texture and visual appeal to meet consumer expectations.

3 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that instrumental texture measurements can reliably predict consumer preferences for fufu, as evidenced by the strong correlations between hedonic consumer testing and Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA). Consumers tend to prefer fufu with lower hardness and adhesiveness, and higher cohesiveness and springiness. Additionally, key textural attributes like mouldability and smoothness, stickiness, and stretchability are closely linked to biochemical factors such as free sugar, swelling power, solubility and amylopectin levels.

The findings have significant implications for cassava breeders and food technologists seeking to optimize fufu quality. By focusing on traits such as reduced hardness and adhesiveness, and improving springiness and cohesiveness, breeders can develop cassava varieties that meet consumer demands for superior fufu texture. Moreover, understanding the influence of biochemical components on sensory qualities provides a pathway for fine-tuning fufu processing techniques and selecting cultivars that deliver the best consumer experience. Balancing both texture and color attributes will be key to enhancing the overall quality and marketability of fufu products.

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